

Research Mentoring Philosophy & Expectation-Setting

A mentor-mentee relationship is a valuable investment that pays dividends for all parties. Through this relationship, I will get to know you, my mentee, and understand your goals, empowering you to navigate the path to your dreams. This relationship likewise will allow you to know me as a role model and a supporter. My goal is to establish an authentic, respectful, nurturing relationship that will last long beyond the formal research mentoring time frame.

Research mentor principles I will employ:

1. **Create a safe environment.** I want you to see me not only as a source of information and support, but also as someone you can trust and be vulnerable with about your professional and academic struggles and weaknesses. I will be patient and open-minded while being flexible to honor your needs. Empathy goes a long way in developing a safe environment.
2. **Maintain focus on the goals.** This starts with defining attainable goals. I will help you focus the scope of their research efforts to achieve your desired goals. I keep you accountable to your goals by consistently praising milestones reached and articulating the next steps towards goal attainment, including discussion of potential barriers, both internal and external. It is important to understand that research progress is often incremental.
3. **Share my path.** Research involves failure. Critical perseverance is necessary for success. Imposter syndrome can creep in. I share my own failures and successes so that I can pass along knowledge and enthusiasm gained. Research is a process; my being process-oriented models an outlook that focuses on the journey as well as the destination.
4. **Instill independence.** Ultimately, I want you to learn enough from me and the mentoring process to become an independent researcher who is ethical and efficient. I require you to be accountable and self-aware. To this end, I provide honest and candid feedback on your skills development and progress towards goal achievement.
5. **Learn from every encounter.** Through our interactions, we will both grow as researchers. I will remain engaged in the mentoring process so that I can evaluate my own effectiveness as a mentor. As I expect you to maintain a growth mindset, I too will appreciate my own capacity and ability to grow. As with research, mentoring is a process.

I can't wait to see what we learn and how we grow!